

BUILDING THE FUTURE OF COURSE CATALOGUES

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ABSTRACT

Student mobility under Erasmus+ is central to the European Higher Education Area. Yet, students often face obstacles in selecting institutions and securing academic recognition due to fragmented, outdated, and non-interoperable course catalogues (CCs). This “information gap” complicates student decision-making and burdens academic coordinators. The Erasmus+-funded project Digitising Academic Catalogues for Enhanced Mobility (DACEM) addresses these challenges by co-creating an open-source, multilingual, and interoperable digital platform. Emphasising usability, transparency, and inclusiveness, DACEM enables students to search, filter, and compare courses, while providing staff with standardised data for recognition and credit transfer. This paper presents the project’s rationale, co-creation methodology, and architecture, showing how DACEM re-engineers CCs to reduce uncertainty, strengthen recognition, and enhance equity in Erasmus+ mobility.

1. Introduction

The Erasmus programme, initially launched in 1987 under the acronym European Region Action Scheme for the Mobility of University Students, was designed to promote academic exchange and intercultural learning by enabling students to pursue part of their studies at partner institutions across Europe. Since its inception, Erasmus has become one of the most significant mobility schemes in higher education worldwide, offering students unique opportunities to enrich their studies and broaden their cultural horizons (Papatsiba, 2006; European Commission, 2023). While initially limited to European Union (EU) member states, the programme progressively expanded to associated and partner countries beyond Europe, reflecting the global dimension of higher education cooperation.

Institutionally, Erasmus has evolved through several policy frameworks. In 1995, it became part of the Socrates programme, and in 2007 it was integrated into the Lifelong Learning Programme (LLP). A significant reform occurred in 2014, when Erasmus+ was launched to consolidate all EU education, training, youth, and sport initiatives under one umbrella. Erasmus+ not only continued to promote mobility but also sought to enhance the quality and strengthen the European dimension of higher education through transnational cooperation, transparency, and improved recognition of qualifications (European Commission, 2014; Kehm, 2019).

From its inception, the Erasmus programme has been underpinned by fundamental principles and instruments that make mobility operational:

- **Course catalogues (CCs):** A key reference point for both sending and host institutions, enabling the comparison of academic offers and the identification of equivalent study opportunities.
- **Inter-institutional bilateral agreements:** These agreements define the availability of modules and courses in advance, ensuring students can realistically select a study pathway abroad.
- **Learning agreements:** These are signed by the student and sending and receiving institutions before the mobility begins and require up-to-date and transparent course catalogue information.

Despite its achievements, Erasmus+ has faced persistent structural challenges. For 36 years, generations of students have reported difficulties accessing accurate, transparent, and comparable information on host institutions' academic offerings. Surveys reveal that many course catalogues are incomplete, not updated regularly, or inconsistent in format, making it difficult for students to choose suitable destinations or prepare learning agreements. Typical student concerns include unclear or outdated course descriptions, lack of information on evaluation mechanisms, insufficient guidance on enrollment procedures, and inconsistencies in workload and credit allocation (ESN, 2021; Wächter, 2014).

These limitations are not only a matter of convenience but also directly affect recognition processes. According to the 2021 Erasmus Student Network (ESN) Survey, fewer than 80% of Erasmus students reported receiving full recognition of their study achievements abroad, well below the target of automatic recognition set by the European Education Area (ESN, 2021). Such shortcomings hinder the programme's capacity to achieve its full potential regarding equity, transparency, and academic integration across borders.

Against this backdrop, the Erasmus+-funded project Digitising Academic Catalogues for Enhanced Mobility (DACEM) was launched to tackle the persistent challenges surrounding course catalogues in higher education. DACEM aims to provide a sustainable, open-source, multilingual, and interoperable platform for course information that ensures institutions can deliver accessible, complete, consistent, and up-to-date data. The project contributes to greater transparency, efficiency, and trust in academic mobility by re-engineering course catalogues and aligning them with European interoperability standards.

2. Needs analysis on facilitating student mobility through Erasmus+

The Erasmus Charter for Higher Education (ECHE) Monitoring Guide (European Commission, 2023a) highlights the role of course catalogues (CCs) in ensuring transparency and quality in mobility. Institutions must publish and regularly update CCs well before mobility periods, while Erasmus+ National Agencies monitor criteria such as timely publication, completeness, accessibility, and availability in widely spoken languages.

Despite these requirements, digitising CCs remains difficult due to decentralised academic cultures, technical complexity, and limited resources (Kehm, 2019; Wächter, 2014). Many HEIs still rely on static PDFs or fragmented web pages that are rarely interoperable or multilingual (European Commission, 2015). This undermines transparency and complicates learning agreements.

The Erasmus Student Network (ESN, 2021) reports frequent student complaints about outdated or inaccessible information, while alliances such as EUF and Athena stress the need for interoperable tools to coordinate curricula (Reichert, 2019).

DACEM responds to these challenges by addressing key needs:

- **Transparency:** Clear and consistent course information.
- **Mobility:** Comparability and recognition of achievements.
- **Efficiency:** Streamlined workflows for staff.
- **Accreditation:** Reliable data supporting quality assurance (ENQA, 2015).

By tackling these needs, DACEM contributes to the European Education Area and the Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027 (European Commission, 2020), advancing transparency, inclusiveness, and the digital transformation of HEIs.

3. DACEM objectives

The main objective of the DACEM project is to enhance student mobility within European higher education institutions by addressing long-standing challenges in the accessibility, usability, and interoperability of course catalogues. In line with the principles ECTS Users' Guide (European Commission, 2015), DACEM aims to modernise CCs through digitalisation, standardisation, and integration with existing European infrastructures, thereby strengthening transparency, recognition, and comparability of qualifications across borders.

This overarching objective can be articulated through the following specific goals:

Mapping the current landscape of course catalogues

Conducting a comprehensive analysis of the state of CCs in European HEIs, with particular attention to institutional practices, technical limitations, and recurring problems in maintaining timely and up-to-date course information (Wächter, 2014).

Developing technical guidance and standards

Offering clear recommendations to institutions on how to design and maintain digital CCs that ensure accessibility for end-users, consistency of content, operational timeliness, and interoperability with other systems, including Erasmus Without Paper (EWP) and the Online Learning Agreement (OLA).

Creating an open-source digital solution

Designing a flexible CC platform supporting the effective management of course digital descriptions and providing application programming interfaces (APIs) to facilitate seamless integration with mobility tools and institutional information systems (Reichert, 2019).

Optimising administrative workflows

Streamlining processes in accordance with ECTS guidelines, enhancing the efficiency of academic and administrative staff responsible for course data management. This reduces redundancies, limits errors, and supports sustainable digital practices in higher education administration.

Improving student experience

Ensuring CCs are more useful, transparent, and reliable for students preparing for mobility. This includes more explicit course descriptions, up-to-date evaluation and enrollment details, and improved comparability between institutions, empowering students to make better-informed academic choices (ESN, 2021).

Leveraging new technologies

Exploring the potential of advanced tools, such as semantic web technologies, to improve the management, searchability, and personalisation of course catalogue data, supporting more innovative and more efficient mobility processes (Veletsianos, 2020).

Supporting European University alliances

Facilitating joint educational offers by enabling interconnected CC instances through API implementation. This reduces redundant data entry across repositories and strengthens collaboration with the European Universities Initiative (European Commission, 2022).

These objectives support the creation of a more interconnected European Higher Education Area (EHEA), where the ECTS framework fosters transparency, recognition, and comparability of qualifications (Kehm, 2019). By digitising course catalogues in line with ECTS, HEIs can improve mobility, recognition, and institutional capacities for quality assurance and resource management. DACEM also contributes to the digital and green transitions outlined in the Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027 (European Commission, 2020), ensuring course information

is accessible, consistent, and inclusive. In doing so, it enhances equity and opens mobility opportunities for diverse student groups, moving towards a more sustainable, transparent, and student-centred European higher education system.

4. Methodology

The DACEM project adopts a co-creation methodology that places students and academic staff at the centre of platform design. Co-creation in higher education ensures that solutions are robust, relevant, and aligned with stakeholder needs (Bovill & Woolmer, 2019; Healey, Flint, & Harrington, 2014). By involving end-users throughout the lifecycle, DACEM enhances the usability and sustainability of its course catalogue solution.

The framework consists of three components:

- **Qualitative research:** Interviews and focus groups with students, coordinators, staff, and administrators to capture experiences of mobility and course management challenges (Klemenčič, 2016).
- **Mapping studies:** A review of CC systems across HEIs, assessing structures, formats, accessibility, and alignment with the ECTS Users' Guide (European Commission, 2015).
- **Comparative analysis:** Cross-country study of practices in Estonia, France, Greece, Hungary, Portugal, Slovenia, and Spain, highlighting differences between centralised and decentralised approaches (Teichler, 2017).

Findings show that students need transparent, filterable, multilingual, and mobile-friendly catalogues; coordinators require interoperability with Erasmus Without Paper (EWP) and Online Learning Agreements (OLA); and many HEIs lack the resources to redesign their CCs independently.

This mixed-method approach ensures DACEM's outputs are evidence-based, adaptable across diverse contexts, and aligned with the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) and the European Education Area (EEA) goals.

5. Platform design and architecture

The architecture of DACEM platform has been designed to balance openness, scalability, interoperability, and usability, in line with the digitalisation goals set out by the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) and the Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027 (European Commission, 2020). The technical design ensures that institutions of varying sizes and capacities can adopt the platform through on-premise deployment or cloud-based services. Core design principles of the platform implementation include:

Open-source foundation

The platform is built as an open-source solution to foster transparency, adaptability, and long-term sustainability. Open-source approaches in higher education digitalisation ensure that institutions retain control over their data and can adapt the system to their local needs while contributing to a collective knowledge base (Reichert, 2019).

Standards compliance and interoperability

The architecture supports interoperability with Erasmus Without Paper (EWP), Online Learning Agreements (OLA), and the Network of Recognition of Modules (NORM) to align with European mobility infrastructures. Adherence to standards such as the ECTS Users' Guide (European Commission, 2015) and FAIR principles for data management (Wilkinson et al., 2016) ensures that course information is structured, machine-readable, and reusable across institutional and national systems.

User-centered design

The system prioritises accessibility, multilingualism, and mobile responsiveness. Informed by stakeholder feedback, the architecture integrates features allowing students to filter, compare, and access course information seamlessly, ensuring that staff interfaces are intuitive and efficient.

Technical stack

The DACEM platform architecture integrates widely used, robust technologies:

- **Content Management System (CMS):** Drupal 10, providing modularity, multi-site support, and extensive APIs for integration.
- **Backend:** PHP 8.3 and MariaDB 10.6+, ensuring reliability, security, and scalability.
- **Frontend:** Bootstrap and JavaScript frameworks for responsive, mobile-friendly user experiences.
- **Deployment options:** Flexible architecture enabling both on-premise HEI-managed hosting and cloud-based solutions.

This stack was chosen to ensure broad institutional uptake, reduce technical barriers to adoption, and guarantee compatibility with existing IT infrastructures (Open Source Initiative, 2022).

Functional layers

The architecture consists of three interrelated layers:

- **Data layer:** Structured storage of course information in machine-readable formats, supporting multilingual content and metadata aligned with ECTS descriptors (learning outcomes, credits, workload, and assessment).
- **Application layer:** APIs for integration with mobility tools (EWP, OLA), data validation services, and workflows for catalogue maintenance. This layer supports automated updates and reduces redundancies in administrative processes.
- **Presentation layer:** User-facing interfaces for students, coordinators, and staff. This includes multilingual search and filtering tools, responsive design for mobile use, and dashboards for academic staff managing catalogue entries.

Security and sustainability

Security is embedded throughout the architecture, with measures to prevent SQL injection, cross-site scripting (XSS), and role-based authentication to protect sensitive data. Compliance with GDPR protect personal and institutional data (European Data Protection Board, 2021).

Sustainability is achieved through modular design, allowing HEIs to integrate additional functionalities (e.g., semantic search, big data analytics) without disrupting core services. This future-proofing approach aligns with calls for flexible and adaptive infrastructures in higher education digitalisation (Gaebel et al., 2021).

Figure 1. DACEM system architecture.

6. Conclusion and call to action

The DACEM project addresses a core barrier to Erasmus+ mobility: the lack of transparent, accessible, and interoperable course catalogues. By closing this gap, DACEM advances the goals of the European Education Area, promoting transparency, recognition, and inclusiveness. It enhances academic planning with structured, multilingual data, strengthens credit transfer through standardised formats, improves accessibility, and builds student confidence with reliable information. More than a technical tool, DACEM is a step toward higher education's digital transformation, offering an open-source, co-created, and sustainable platform that supports students, staff, and Europe's digital and green transitions.

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